

THE USE OF ELECTRONIC PORTFOLIOS FOR SHAPING THE COMPETENCIES OF HUMANITARIAN SUBJECT TEACHERS IN VOCATIONAL SCHOOLS

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Abstract: In this article, effective proposals for the use of the educational portfolio in the formation of the skills of using ICT tools of the teachers of the humanities of the vocational schools have been given.

Key words: ICT competencies, professional education, educational portfolio, authoring software tools, Web technologies

Has proven effective in enhancing the attention, curiosity, independent thinking, and creative activities of students, as well as improving information acquisition, processing, synthesis, generalization, and summarization. The use of e-learning resources in the educational process significantly contributes to the global awareness and intellectual development of the younger generation.

In order to shape the ICT competencies of humanitarian subject teachers in vocational schools, it is essential to develop strategies for utilizing contemporary information and communication technologies in pedagogical practices. The electronic portfolio for "Shaping ICT Competencies of Humanitarian Subject Teachers in Vocational Schools" includes theoretical and practical materials that highlight the capabilities of the Microsoft Office suite (Word, Excel, PowerPoint, Publisher, Access) and their applications. It aims to make learning activities engaging, ensure the relevance of acquired knowledge, and increase students' interest in the subject matter.

The portfolio emphasizes the importance of utilizing technical equipment such as computers, input and output devices, display and multimedia devices, and network devices in vocational schools for the effective use of information and communication technologies. Video materials are provided to demonstrate the capabilities of these technical tools and the ways in which teachers can incorporate them into their teaching methods.

To enhance the competency of humanitarian subject teachers in vocational schools, the portfolio focuses on the creation of electronic teaching and didactic materials using authoring tools such as Articulate Storyline, Adobe Captivate, Adobe Flash, CourseLab, iSpring, and Lectora. Each e-learning authoring tool adheres to standards such as SCORM, TinCan, HTML5, AICC, and

LTI. Additionally, theoretical and video materials are provided for developing skills in creating e-learning resources for LMS systems using SCORM, TinCan, API, or AICC standards.

The portfolio addresses the need for web technology proficiency in teaching computer networks and file sharing methods. It provides theoretical and video materials to explain web technology concepts and principles. The integration of multimedia capabilities of computers is highlighted as a key factor in improving the quality and effectiveness of the educational process.

Ensuring information security, protecting against unauthorized access, maintaining the functionality of information systems and software, preventing alteration, deletion, or unauthorized access to other information, and adhering to rules governing information access, dissemination, and protection are essential considerations for shaping the competencies of humanitarian subject teachers. Practical tips, theoretical knowledge, and video instructions on information security are included in the relevant section of the portfolio.

The portfolio encourages the use of mobile learning and participation in public online courses for humanitarian subject teachers in vocational schools. It suggests utilizing information from the portfolio for creating instructional materials, assignments, and evaluation criteria. Moreover, the portfolio includes video tutorials for accessing necessary and essential information using search engines such as Google, Google Chrome, Internet Explorer, Yandex, Nigma, FireFox, and YaCy.

It covers topics related to sending information over computer networks, collaborative use of computers, specialization of each computer for specific tasks, and accessing electronic mail services using national domain email services. Theoretical and video materials are provided in the portfolio for the proficiency of humanitarian subject teachers in vocational schools.

To organize an effective learning process, enhance learning outcomes, and stimulate students' intellectual development, the portfolio suggests the use of multimedia technologies in arranging educational activities. Materials for creating electronic textbooks, resources, multimedia applications, virtual laboratories, educational games, and modern testing tools are also provided in the portfolio under the section "Shaping ICT Competencies."

In conclusion, the information and teaching methods provided in this portfolio can be efficiently utilized to shape the ICT competencies of humanitarian subject teachers in vocational schools.

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